

Analysis and assessment of medical-economic indicators for the activities of the in-hospital department of the University Hospital "Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL" in the period 2013–2024

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Abstract

Hospital activities, and in-hospital activities in particular, represent one of the most resource-intensive parts of the health system, and their effectiveness depends to a significant extent on the rational management of financial costs. This study analyzes the dynamics of basic medical-economic indicators – average cost per patient, daily costs divided by the number of hospital beds (daily cost per bed), average cost of medications per day (medication cost per day), and cost of food per day (food cost per day) – at University Hospital "Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL" for the period 2013–2024, in order to assess their role as indicators of the effectiveness of in-hospital activities. The results show a clear trend toward increasing costs, reflecting the influence of inflationary processes, pandemic factors, and the increasing complexity of treatment, while at the same time highlighting stable components within the cost structure. The analysis emphasizes the importance of quantitative indicators as a tool for management planning and for formulating strategies to increase the economic sustainability of hospital activities.

Keywords

assessment, dynamics, hospital, inpatient activity, medical-economic indicators

Introduction

Hospital care is one of the most resource-intensive sectors of the health system and includes a complex set of diagnostic, treatment, rehabilitation, and support activities carried out under hospital conditions. It guarantees the provision of continuous, specialized medical care for patients with acute, chronic, or life-threatening diseases requiring professional monitoring and technologically supported treatment (Cylus et al. 2016; World Health

Organization 2017, 2022). Hospital activity represents a structural core of hospital organization, in which a significant proportion of the human, material, and financial resources of medical institutions are concentrated. Effective management of this activity is a key condition for the sustainability of hospital structures, especially in the context of limited budgets and growing demand for health services (Kirkov 2023; Mahomedradja et al. 2024).

The assessment of hospital activity traditionally includes an analysis of both qualitative and quantitative

medical-economic indicators, but it is precisely the financial quantitative indicators that provide the clearest information on economic efficiency and cost adequacy. Among these indicators, the average annual cost per patient, which reflects the overall resource intensity of hospital treatment, and the average daily cost per bed, which measures the cost of providing 24-hour hospital care (Hollingsworth et al. 2009), are of particular importance. In addition, the average cost of medications per day is an important indicator for assessing investments in pharmacological treatment – a key factor in the quality of medical care – while the cost of food per day represents part of the maintenance costs associated with ensuring patient comfort and physiological care (OECD 2006, 2022; Papanicolas and Smith 2013).

International organizations such as WHO and OECD emphasize that monitoring and analyzing cost indicators are essential components of hospital system management and provide a basis for planning, budgeting, and resource optimization (OECD 2006, 2022; World Health Organization 2017). Financial indicators allow assessment of the level of hospital utilization, productivity, and sustainability, as well as identification of possible imbalances between costs and activity levels (Busse et al. 2011; Cylus et al. 2016). In addition, they support strategic management by providing information necessary for analyzing cost structures, assessing efficiency, and setting priorities in the allocation of budgetary resources.

In a dynamic healthcare environment characterized, on the one hand, by continuous technological progress and increasing requirements for medical effectiveness and, on the other hand, by limited financial resources, the analysis of medical-economic indicators is gaining increasing importance. Such analysis allows assessment of the real value of inpatient care, tracking of trends over time, and formulation of management decisions aimed at improving efficiency and economic sustainability at the hospital level (World Health Organization 2017, 2018, 2019; Schreyögg et al. 2008).

In this context, the assessment of quantitative indicators for inpatient activity – such as the average cost per discharged patient, daily cost per bed, daily cost of medications, and cost of food per day – for the period 2013–2024, together with tracking their changes and evaluating influencing factors, provides a basis for an objective assessment of the cost-effectiveness of inpatient activity and contributes to the formulation of guidelines for improving the financial management of the medical institution.

The purpose of this article is to examine and analyze the structure and dynamics of quantitative medical-economic indicators for the activities of the inpatient unit of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” during the period 2013–2024.

Materials and methodology of the research

The object of this scientific study is the structure and dynamics of quantitative medical-economic indicators for the activity of the inpatient unit of University Hospital

“Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” for the period 2013–2024, as well as the factors influencing them.

The study was conducted based on reporting data and statistical information provided by the medical institution, including tables and graphs reflecting the dynamics of inpatient activity during the study period. The analysis employed both absolute and relative indicators, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the volume, intensity, and effectiveness of hospital care.

A range of sociological, statistical, and documentary methods was used in conducting the study, as follows:

- descriptive statistical analysis – to present the current state and volume of activity;
- comparative and dynamic analysis – to examine changes over time;
- graphical methods – for visualizing trends;
- calculation of averages and relative values.

Results and discussion

The activities of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” are organized into 25 specialized clinics, departments, and clinical diagnostic structures. In order to make a realistic forecast and provide adequate guidelines for the development of hospital activities, a comprehensive analysis and assessment of medical-economic indicators for the medical activities performed in the inpatient department is required. This approach makes it possible to proactively identify problems facing the hospital and to formulate strategic priorities for its development.

A software product has been implemented at University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” to track and provide information on the main medical-economic indicators of hospital activity. This information is necessary for the timely identification of significant deviations in indicator values and for supporting prompt and informed management decisions.

During the analyzed period 2013–2024, the average annual cost per patient showed a clear upward trend, which is typical of hospital systems operating under conditions of increasing healthcare costs. The observed almost twofold increase by 2020 was strongly influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to higher expenditures for medications, consumables, protective equipment, disinfection, and additional staff remuneration. In 2021, a further significant increase was recorded, reflecting the high burden of hospitalized cases and the increased cost of treatment under conditions of an ongoing epidemic wave.

Despite a slight decrease in 2022, the overall trend remained steadily upward, with expenditures at the end of the period more than twice as high as those in 2013. This dynamic reflects the combined effects of inflationary processes, more expensive therapeutic practices, rising labor costs, and changes in patient structure, including an increasing share of cases requiring highly specialized treat-

ment. In this context, the indicator highlights the need for a detailed analysis of the cost structure and an active search for opportunities for rationalization without compromising the quality of medical care.

Figure 1. Average annual cost per patient – BGN. **Source:** Financial statement of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

The average cost per hospital bed also increased substantially during the analyzed period, with the total increase exceeding fourfold. The most pronounced rise was observed in 2020, when the pandemic situation required a significant expansion of resource provision in hospital wards. This sharp increase resulted from the need for more intensive use of medications, consumables, protective equipment, and additional infection control measures.

In subsequent years, the upward trend was maintained, with a further increase observed in 2024. This reflects the rising cost of hospital stays driven by inflation, increased energy prices, changes in therapeutic algorithms, and higher personnel costs. This indicator clearly demonstrates the real financial burden associated with hospital bed utilization and serves as an important reference point for analyzing the efficiency and sustainability of inpatient activities.

Figure 2. Average cost per hospital bed – BGN. **Source:** Financial statement of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

The average cost of medications per day increased gradually but substantially over the study period, reaching a level more than six times higher at the end than at the beginning. This increase reflects both rising medication prices and changes in therapeutic practices, including the increasingly frequent use of innovative and high-cost medicinal products.

The increase observed in 2020 was particularly pronounced, as the treatment of COVID-19 patients required combinations of antibiotics, anticoagulants, corticosteroids, and other specific medications. The further increase

in 2024 suggests growing treatment complexity and the influence of international trends toward higher pharmaceutical prices. Consequently, this indicator represents a key tool for monitoring the hospital’s therapeutic policy and its financial sustainability.

Figure 3. Average cost of medications per day – BGN. **Source:** Financial statement of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

The cost of meals per day remains the most stable of all analyzed indicators. Throughout the period, it undergoes minimal fluctuations, with values remaining within relatively narrow limits. This stability is due to the hospital’s use of a catering service organized through procedures under the Public Procurement Act, which provides fixed base prices per meal.

The moderate increases observed in 2022 and 2024 reflect general inflationary processes and rising food prices but do not alter the overall trend of stability. The combination of low costs and a positive assessment of food quality in patient surveys suggests effective management of the external service and good control by the hospital administration. This indicator demonstrates that meal costs remain a predictable and well-managed component of the hospital budget.

Figure 4. Average cost of meals per day – BGN. **Source:** Financial statement of University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” EAD.

Inferences and conclusion

The analysis of medical-economic indicators of inpatient activity at University Hospital “Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL” for the period 2013–2024 shows a clearly pronounced trend of increasing costs, reflecting both general econom-

ic conditions and the specific characteristics of hospital activity during this period. The average annual cost per patient demonstrates a steady upward trend, reaching its highest values in the years immediately following the COVID-19 pandemic. This increase results from a combination of factors, including inflationary pressure, rising personnel costs, increased prices of medicinal products and consumables, and changes in the structure and burden of treated patients. The indicator clearly reflects the growing resource intensity of hospital activity, characteristic of modern medical institutions that increasingly apply high-technology and cost-intensive treatment methods.

The average cost per hospital bed also increased significantly during the analyzed period, highlighting the rising cost of providing one day of hospital care. This growth was particularly pronounced during the pandemic years, when the hospital was required to maintain readiness for severe and urgent cases demanding increased resource provision. Post-pandemic cost increases were further influenced by general economic processes and rising prices of energy resources, medical devices, and essential services. This indicator demonstrates a sustained increase in budgetary pressure and underscores the need for continuous process optimization.

The average cost of medications per day proves to be the most sensitive of all analyzed indicators. The substantial increases observed reflect both changes in the pharmaceutical market and the introduction of new therapeutic practices requiring the use of more expensive medicinal products. During the pandemic years, values increased sharply due to heightened consumption and the need for specialized medication regimens. Toward the end of the study period, persistently high values indicate the long-term establishment of more resource-intensive therapeutic approaches associated with the treatment of chronic, complex, and severe diseases. This finding emphasizes the importance of a well-structured drug policy and effective management of medication-related costs.

In contrast to the other indicators, the average cost of food per day remains the most stable over time. Its minimal fluctuations logically result from the nature of the catering service, with pricing determined through procedures under the Public Procurement Act. The slight increases observed in recent years reflect general food price inflation but do not disrupt the long-term trend toward stability. This confirms that food costs are predictable, controllable, and effectively managed within the hospital budget, while patient satisfaction remains high.

In summary, quantitative indicators of inpatient activity clearly show that, during the period 2013–2024, the hospital operated under conditions of increasing resource bur-

den, significant external challenges, and substantial public pressure to maintain high-quality medical care. These trends indicate the need for an integrated approach to cost management, incorporating process optimization, medication cost control, rational resource use, and strategic planning. Despite significant cost increases, the hospital succeeded in maintaining stability across key operational components, reflecting strong organizational sustainability and effective management. The analysis of empirical data underscores the importance of medical-economic indicators as tools for assessing inpatient activity and as a foundation for decision-making aimed at improving both the economic sustainability and quality of hospital care.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

Annual financial report of the University Hospital „Tsaritsa Joanna“ – ISUL

Arah OA, Westert GP, Hurst J, Klazinga NS (2006) A conceptual framework for the OECD health care quality indicators project. Interna-

- tional Journal for Quality in Health Care 18(Suppl 1): 5–13. <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzl023>
- Busse R, Geissler A, Quentin W, Wiley M (2011) Diagnosis-related groups in Europe: Moving towards transparency, efficiency and quality in hospitals. Open University Press, Maidenhead. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-11-271>
- Campbell SM, Roland MO, Buetow SA (2000) Defining quality of care. *Social Science & Medicine* 51(11): 1611–1625. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(00\)00057-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(00)00057-5)
- Copnell B, Hagger V, Wilson SG, Evans SM, Sprivilis PC, Cameron PA (2009) Measuring the quality of hospital care: an inventory of indicators. *Internal Medicine Journal* 39(6): 352–360. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1445-5994.2009.01961.x> [Epub 2009 Mar 23.]
- Cylus J, Papanicolas I, Smith PC (2016) Health system efficiency: How to make measurement matter. WHO Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen.
- Drummond ME, Sculpher MJ, Claxton K, Stoddart GL, Torrance GW (2015) *Methods for the economic evaluation of health care programmes* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- European Commission (2024) Supply and demand model for the health-care workforce in the EU27. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the EU. <https://doi.org/10.2760/957386>
- Eurostat (2023) Healthcare Expenditure Statistics. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Figuerola JF, Frakt AB, Jha AK (2017) Addressing rising health care costs: a view from the front line. *NEJM Catalyst* 3(4): 1–11.
- Hollingsworth JW, Wolf JS, Flanigan RC (2009) Use of hospital cost and bed utilization metrics for evaluating efficiency. *Health Services Research* 44(5 Pt 1): 1573–1592.
- Hussey PS, Wertheimer S, Mehrotra A (2013) The association between health care quality and cost: a systematic review. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 158(1): 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-158-1-201301010-00006>
- Karpova OB, Zagoruychenko AA (2022) Current issues of staffing in healthcare in Russia and in the world. *Russian Journal of Social Medicine* 66(3): 181–187. <https://doi.org/10.47470/0044-197X-2022-66-3-181-187>
- Kirkov V (2023) A training quality optimisation model for the undergraduate internship in Medical university – Sofia, Sofia 2023. PhD Thesis, Medical University of Sofia.
- Law on medical institutions in the Republic of Bulgaria (2025) Law on medical institutions in the Republic of Bulgaria. <https://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2134670848>
- Mahomedradja RF, Tichelaar J, Mokkink LB, Sigaloff KCE, Agtmael MA (2024) Quality indicators for appropriate in-hospital pharmacotherapeutic stewardship: An international modified Delphi study. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology* 90(5): 1280–1300. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.16015> [Epub 2024 Feb 18.]
- Ministry of Health (MH) (2022) Report on the health of healthcare in the Republic of Bulgaria. Ministry of Health, Sofia.
- OECD (2006) Health Care Quality Indicators Project: Conceptual Framework. OECD Publishing, Paris.
- OECD (2023) Health at a Glance 2023: OECD Indicators. OECD Publishing, Paris. [doi:10.1787/health_glance-2023-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/health_glance-2023-en)
- Papanicolas I, Smith PC (2013) *Health System Performance Comparison*. Open University Press, Maidenhead.
- Schreyögg J, Stargardt T, Velasco-Garrido M, Busse R (2008) Defining the “efficiency frontier” in the economic evaluation of health care interventions. *Health Economics* 17(3): 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.1268>
- World Health Organization (2017) Health workforce and labor market dynamics in OECD high-income countries: A synthesis of recent analyses and simulations of future supply and requirements. WHO, Geneva. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/259361>
- World Health Organization (2018) Handbook for National Quality Policy and Strategy: A Practical Approach to Developing Policy and Strategy to Improve Quality of Care. WHO, Geneva.
- World Health Organization (2019) The Global Action Plan for Healthy Lives and Well-being for All (SDG3 GAP). <https://www.who.int/initiatives/sdg3-global-action-plan>
- World Health Organization (2022) Global Spending on Health: Weathering the Storm. WHO, Geneva.
- World Health Organization (2023) World Health Statistics. WHO, Geneva.